

LIFE SKILLS ACQUIRED BY STUDENTS ENROLLED IN THE PHYSICAL EDUCATION DEPARTMENT OF AL-QUDS UNIVERSITY

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Abstract:

The present study aims at investigating the life management skills acquired by students enrolled in the Physical Education Department at Al-Quds University. The study population included all third and fourth year students of the Physical Education Department of the academic year 2014/2015. The study sample consisted of 67 male and female students who were selected purposively. To achieve the objectives of the study, a questionnaire was designed as an instrument for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of 45 items distributed over five domains, namely, physical and efficiency skills, thinking and discovery skills, mental skills, social skills and communication skills. The researchers applied the content validity approach to calculate the validity of the study. The researchers, as well, applied Cronbach's alpha scale to calculate the internal consistency coefficient of the study instrument as a whole. The findings of the study showed that the life skills acquired by the students of the Department of Physical Education are higher in level than all other study disciplines and that there were no significant differences in the acquired life skills of the sample individuals pertaining to the variables of sex, academic level and place of residence. The researchers, consequently, recommended that various life skills should be integrated in the academic process and that the educational experiences should be connected to different life experiences. The researchers, further, recommended that certain courses and workshops should be organized to explain to university educators and students the concept of life skills and how they can be integrated in academic curricula.

Keywords: life skills, physical education students, academic curricula

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1. Introduction

The educational process has a significant role in determining the future of nations. Therefore, most countries of today's world are working on promoting all aspects of education to meet the needs and advances of the present time. Thus, the rapid changes in today's life have always inspired nations to reconsider their educational systems, where modern education seeks to enable learners to grow up and be able to use the best of one's educational capabilities.

Since academic institutions are the environment of awareness, thought, and knowledge, those in charge should persistently work on how to provide human societies with trained and qualified individuals through integrating education, research, and community service. Moreover, these institutions should take care of, make use of, and promote youth capabilities. They should, as well, qualify leaders to be able to shoulder responsibility in all aspects of life so as to face different life experiences and challenges (Masa'deh, 2008).

Life skills play a major and vital role in employing the youth and turning them into an active investment element in the development process based on its comprehensive and integrated concept. Consequently, they should receive extra attention and training to achieve both active and interactive co-existence in the community of cognitive economy which is based on the best investment of creative human abilities. In this context, I should maintain that life skills usually differ from one individual to another and from one society to another, as well as from one time to another; therefore the individual who wants to keep pace with modern changes and developments is the one who can acquire life skills from the very beginning so as to gain the scientific method and apply it in thinking, decision making, seeking for knowledge, problem solving, creative and critical thinking, cooperative collective work, communication tactics, respecting others, self-learning, inference, problem solving, etc. (Soteri, 2008).

Teaching students the various skills beside the academic skills is crucial since the individual assessment criteria depend these days on what a human is able to do, rather than on what he/she knows. Therefore, investing in the human force is, for sure, beneficent since it increases their opportunities to find employment and receive higher salaries as a result of good training, qualifications, and diversity of experiences.

According to Al-Sayed (2007), life skills can be defined as the personal and social behaviors and skills an individual needs in order to confidently and efficiently manage his/her life and interact with other people in the society. This, as Al-Sayed maintains, entails taking the right decisions, holding personal and social responsibilities, self-

understanding, understanding of others, building good relations with society members, avoiding crises, and the ability to think and create things.

The researchers of this study define life skills as the ability to tactically deal and interact with life experiences and challenges in order to adapt to modern life needs. As such, the researchers in the present study argue that different life skills should be integrated in various educational curricula at all stages in order to have graduates who possess the adequate abilities and skills needed enable them to perfectly and efficiently play their different roles in life.

1.1 Significance of the Study

The present study tackles an up-to-date topic in the educational process; it is the life skills students need to acquire beside the educational experiences in order to succeed in real life situations and experiences.

So, the importance of the present study can be exemplified in the following:

1. This study focuses on academic education, where students are exposed to a group of educational experiences applicable to life skills that will enable them to easily deal with the demands of modern technology.
2. The findings of the study will likely benefit those involved in the field of physical education, namely, officials, educators, professors, and inspectors through drawing attention to the importance of integrating life skills in the curriculum.
3. The study will probably open the door for further studies in the field in question, which in turn will aid and support the results of the present study.

1.2 Problem of the Study

These days, we are in urgent need for educational outcomes that go with and meet the requirements of rapid technological and scientific developments. Therefore, universities shoulder the responsibility for training and qualifying generations who possess the life management skills that enable them to confidently manage their lives and deal with the people they interact with. In this context, I should mention that the World Health Organization defines life management skills as the capabilities which enable individuals to act positively in a way that allows them to effectively deal with the needs and challenges of everyday life (Omar, 2009).

In fact, today's age of cognitive economy needs special skills to help us become creative and productive. Such skills are acquired mainly from the curricula of the educational institutions which integrate educational experiences and life skills. Accordingly, these curricula should be comprehensive, in the meaning that they should meet the needs and desires of learners and qualify them to cope with life experiences

such as creative thinking, decision making, social interaction, holding responsibility, self-respect, tolerance, and self-awareness (Al-Hayek, 2008).

The case being so, the researchers argue that the educational process should not be restricted to merely providing academic information and experiences to students. It, rather, should provide students with a variety of skills, experiences and codes of behavior to enable them to adjust to life needs through building one's personality as a whole.

Thus, the present study was designed to explore the following life skills:

1. Basic life management skills, including communication, writing, reading, and formal and informal correspondence.
2. Analytical life management skills, including problem solving, searching for information, and technology assimilation.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This study aims at investigating two things:

1. The life skills acquired by students enrolled in the Physical Education Department at Al-Quds University.
2. The life skills acquired by the students of the Physical Education Department according to the variables of gender, academic level, and place of residence.

1.4 Questions of the Study

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the life management skills acquired by the students of the Physical Education Department at Al-Quds University?
2. Are there any statistically significant differences at the level of $0.05 \geq \alpha$ as for the students' academic levels pertaining to the variables of sex, academic level and place of residence?

1.5 Limitations of the Study

1. Temporal limit, which shows that the study was carried out during the academic year of 2014-2015.
2. Human limit, which shows that the study was performed on the third and fourth year students enrolled in the Physical Education Department of Al-Quds University at Abu Dies, West Bank.
3. Spatial Limit, which shows that the study was done at the Department of Physical Education, Al-Quds University.

2. Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies

2.1 The Concept of life Skills

Belotte (2005) defines life skills as the abilities that individuals possess and employ in real life situations, which helps them to positively adapt to and face the needs of modern life. Al-Hayek (2010) defines life skills as a group of performances associated with the mental, physical, social, and emotional capabilities through which an individual can solve everyday life problems and interact effectively with the surrounding people in a way that matches the needs of modern life as well as the needs of the work market.

2.2 Classification of Life Skills

Mustafa (2005) classified life skills as in the following model:

1. Emotional skills, such as controlling emotions, bearing pressures, improving willpower, flexibility to adapt, self-esteem, appreciation and respecting of others, tolerance, and the ability to keep up with life changes and developments;
2. Social skills, such as taking responsibility, self-respect, cooperative work, the ability to establish relations, taking the right decisions, the ability to negotiate, and the ability to communicate;
3. Mental abilities, including critical thinking, creative thinking, self-learning, continuous learning, discovery, research and experimentation, recognizing relations, and prediction abilities.

Omran et al. (2001) classified life skills as in the following model:

1. Mental skills, including reading, writing, mathematics, communication;
2. decision making, problem-solving, planning, time and effort management, self-control, human and natural resources management, creative thinking, critical thinking, conflict management, negotiation management, and crises management skills;
3. Practical and manual skills, including caring for the body, dressing and clothes arrangement, preparing food, handling tools and devices, choosing the house, house arrangement, use of environmental resources, and rationalized consumption skills.

The team of career and technical education of the Wisconsin department of public instruction (2008) classified life skills into the following:

1. Basic life skills, including communication, writing, reading, formal and informal correspondence skills;

2. Analytical life skills, including problem-solving, science and technology, and searching for information skills;
3. Interactive skills, including conflict management, citizenship, career development, learning, tolerance, and time management skills.

The Palestinian Ministry of Education (2003) classified life skills into the skills of awareness, decision making, communication and correspondence, personal relations, creative thinking, critical thinking, managing emotions, and coping with pressures.

2.3 Previous Studies

Al-Hayek and Makhlof (2011) conducted a study to investigate the impact of using a Multi-level method of instruction on how seventh graders acquire certain life skills and some basic tennis skills. The sample of the study included 40 male and female students of UNRWA schools in Southern Amman in the first semester of the scholastic year 2010-2011. To achieve the goals of the study, both researchers applied the semi-experimental technique since it suits the nature of the study. They also applied the appropriate statistical methods.

The findings of the study showed that the multi-level method had a positive role in teaching students the life skills needed to build their personalities. They, further, showed that the method of teaching also had a positive impact on improving the subjects' levels of performance in tennis (shooting with one hand, chest pass, peaceful shooting, and dribbling). In view of the results of this study, both researchers recommend the integration of the life skills in question with the curriculum of general physical education and with the curriculum of tennis in particular. They also called for diversifying instruction methods in physical education classes.

Wafi (2010) carried out a study which aimed at investigating how acquired life skills influence the IQ of the secondary stage students. The researcher applied the descriptive analytical method. The population of the study included the secondary school students of Khan Yunis Governorate. The researcher applied Teli list of multi IQs and life skills scale. The study showed that there was statistically significant correlation between the different dimensions of life skills and the different IQs of the secondary stage students, and that the secondary stage students' level of life skills was above the average. The study, further, showed that there were statistically significant differences in the level of life skills of the secondary stage students that could be attributed to the variables of sex and level of education. Meanwhile, there were statistically significant differences pertaining to place of residence (Amal Salh Eldeen).

Al-Bayat (2009) did a study to investigate the integrated curve in the physical education classes which teaches the values and skills of the science subject in the first,

second, and third grades based on life skills. The researcher used the experimental method which as applied on a sample of 244 male and female students of the first three primary grades in Amman's first and fourth education governorates. The researcher designed a pre and post tests for the control and experimental groups as well as three achievement tests and a questionnaire for skills and values. The findings of this study showed that there were differences between the experimental and control groups as to the academic achievement for the benefit of the experimental group, and that there were statistically significant differences between the two groups in the variable of life skills for the benefit of the experimental group.

Al-Weisi (2009) carried out a study to find out the impact of an educational program based on kinetic games in developing life skills (namely, cooperation and collective work, communication, emotion control, self-reliance and responsibility, observing traffic laws, and improving the behavior of exploring things), and the basic kinetic skills of running, jump, balance and catching. The population of the study included the early primary stage students, and the sample consisted of 40 students from Kafr Al-Ma' Primary School for boys in Kura County in Jordan. The researcher divided the sample of the study into an experimental and a control group, where the experimental group was exposed to the proposed school program. The study showed the benefit of the new model in developing the aforementioned life skills and the basic kinetic skills. The study, as well, revealed that there were statistically significant differences between the two groups for the benefit of the experimental group. The researcher recommends the use of the proposed school program in building the basic life and kinetic skills of the early primary stage students. He also urges for adopting relevant curricula and physical and kinetic programs in this stage.

Omar (2009) performed the experimental method in an a study which aimed at exploring the contribution of certain modern physical education pedagogical methods in building up the life skills (namely, the physical, communication, social and collaborative, mental and ethical, and thinking and discovery skills) through football and volleyball. The sample of the study consisted of 76 students who were selected randomly from 275 first year undergraduates enrolled in the physical education program at Abd Al-Hameed Bin Badis School in Algeria. The study showed that the two methods had a positive impact on building life skills, and the results were for the benefit of the post tests performed on each game. The researcher recommends that teachers should diversify the implementation of experiences depending on the variation of pedagogical experiences, and that life skills should be integrated in the curriculum of physical education.

Al-Hayek et al (2008) carried out a research to investigate the most important life skills that should be covered by the physical education curriculum of the University of Jordan. The researcher also aimed at investigating how much each skill is demanding in view of the students' opinions and the variable of sex. The sample of the study was selected from the students enrolled in the physical education programs of the University of Jordan, Yarmouk University, Hashemite University and Mu'tah University during the spring semester of the academic year 2007-2008. To test the study hypotheses, the researcher designed a questionnaire consisting of the life skills that should be included in the curricula of gymnasium built on the economy of information in the University of Jordan. The examined life skills were divided into four domains, including the physical and efficiency skills, leadership skills, thinking and discovery skills, and social and mental skills. The findings of the study showed that the University of Jordan curricula of gymnasium had earned students with low level life skills, compared to general life skills. Besides, the study showed that the subjects scored the highest levels in physical and efficiency skills, followed respectively by the skills of thinking and discovery, leadership, and, finally, mental and social skills. The study further showed that there were statistically significant differences between both genders. The differences were for the benefit of the female students, in view of the level of life skills they acquired throughout the gymnasium curricula. However, and according to the study, there were no statistically significant differences in the students points of view attributed to the academic level.

Al-Hayek and Battayneh (2007) conducted a study to examine the nature of integrating life skills in the physical education curricula in view of the students of the University of Jordan. The sample of the study consisted of 240 male and female students from all four academic years. The two researchers applied a scale of 60 items which covered the four domains of physical and efficiency skills, the communication skills, the social and collective work skills, and mental and ethical skills. The findings of the study showed that there was consensus amongst students of physical education that the curricula lacked the adequate number of the necessary life skills. The researchers attributed those results to the incongruence of the curricula with the standards of the overall quality and the lack of diversity of instruction methods focusing on the learner as the core element in the educational process. The researchers recommend the integration of life skills in the curricula of physical education and the use of modern technology, the internet and other media by students.

Al-Sowtery (2007) did a study to investigate the effect of implementing certain instruction methods on employing life skills and how such methods affect the performance level of certain basic skills of volleyball in physical education based on the

economy of knowledge of the curricula. The sample of the study consisted of 112 male and female teachers, 11 inspectors, and 160 male and female seventh grade students from the directorate of education of Amman. The researcher employed both the descriptive and experimental methods. He also worked out a school program of 32 units with 4 methods of instruction and two questionnaires, one targeting inspectors and teachers and other targeting students. The results of the study showed that the skill of leadership came first in the hierarchy; whereas, the skill of problem solving came last, in view of the inspectors and teachers' judgments. The study also showed that there were statistically significant differences between the pre and post scales of life skills as well as in the scale of volleyball basic skills for the benefit of the post scale. The researcher recommends the integration of the life skills pointed to with the economy based physical education knowledge.

Goudas et al. (2005) studied the affectivity of a program of life skills program training intended to athletes joining sports clubs. The researchers designed the program of youth sports as an attempt to positively qualify athletes. They applied the experimental method and selected a sample of 72 athletes, 40 of them were volleyball players and 32 were football players. Their ages were between 10 and 12 years. The skills tested were knowledge, setting objectives, self-respect, problem solving, and positive thinking.

The findings of the study showed that training students on life skills had improved their skills in the games they used to play. The findings also showed that training on life skills had enhanced the students' overall knowledge and the skills they needed to overcome life obstacles. The researcher of this study stresses the importance of training young people on life skills to qualify them to be good citizens and athletes.

Papacharisis et al. (2005) did a study to investigate the impact of building life skills through volleyball and football in Greece. The sample of the study consisted of 40 volleyball players and 32 football players who were selected randomly and whose ages were between 10 and 12 years. The researcher divided the subjects of the study into two groups; the experimental group who received training in both life skills and the skills needed by volleyball and football players, and the control group who only received training in volleyball and football. The program lasted 4 weeks. The findings of the study showed that the experimental group did better in volleyball and football skills. The study also showed that there were statistically significant differences in life skills for the benefit of the experimental group.

Goudas et al. (2006) conducted a study to examine the impact of training on life skills which were taught as part of the physical education program. The sample of the study included 73 seventh grade male and female students who received a brief copy of

Gool Program which was designed to teach life skills via physical education. The program involved exercises on body strength, flexibility, and endurance. The physical training program as well as the life skills program were both implemented on the experimental group. The control group was exposed to a program in physical education in addition to taking a short class on the Olympic Games. The program took 4 weeks and the findings showed that training on life skills could be employed efficiently through the physical education classes.

Weiss et al. (2007) carried out a study which aimed at assessing the affectivity of physical education in qualifying youth. They adopted a program called 'First Tee' which integrated life skills with certain sports games. The sample of the study consisted of 405 students in First Tee program and 159 enrolled in other athletic activities. The study showed that the integration of life skills with golf, for instance, had positive impacts for the benefit of the participants in First Tee program. The positive impact was also manifested in the improvement of the participants' abilities in collective work, emotion control, entrepreneurial spirit, conflict resolution, social behaviors, personal effectiveness, resistance of peer influence, and organized self-learning.

Gould et al. (2007) carried out a study to investigate how football coaches build life skills in secondary schools. The study was carried out at University of North Carolina at Greensboro on a sample of 10 coaches of an average of 54 years of age. The sample of the study was selected purposely from the best coaches through holding interviews to collect data pertaining to the strategies of training adopted by the coaches. The findings of the study showed that the football coaches who participated in the study did not stress only performance but rather trained students on life skills, and that the motivation for success was their desire to develop the athletes' characters. Moreover, this study stresses that coaches should focus on life skills such as setting goals, communication, time management, emotion control, leadership, social awareness, holding responsibility, collective and cooperative work, and self-respect.

Sugiyamak, Shibukra, Nishida, Ito, Sasaki and Isogai (2008) did a study which aimed at examining the characteristics of the life skills integrated in the physical education curriculum. The sample of the study consisted of 34 male and female physical education teachers in Tokyo. The researchers interviewed the subjects to collect data for the purpose of analysis. The study showed that many teachers think that the curriculum helps students build different aspects of their personalities, such as the social, mental, and practical skills. The participants, according to the study, also maintained that the curriculum provides students with the opportunity to pursue off campus learning and training, and that is an efficient tool to build the students' physical skills and to satisfy their desire for leadership.

After reviewing a group of leading studies, the researchers of the present study has come to realize that these studies address the topic of life skills in academic and educational institutions. Those studies vary in terms of their objectives and content, the target group, the methods and tools applied in data collection, and consequently in terms of their results. The researchers made use of those studies, particularly in building his own tool, classifying the procedures of his study and in the discussion of the results. Yet, the present study is distinguished by its unique temporal limit, since it took place in the same period when the Palestinian educational institutions were working on improving the curricula and integrating them with life skills.

3. Methodology and Procedures

The researchers applied the descriptive method because it better suits the nature and objectives of the present study.

3.1 Population of the Study

The population of the present study included all 137 third and fourth year students enrolled in the Department of Physical Education at Al-Quds University in the academic year of 2014-2015.

3.2 Sample of the Study

The sample of the study consisted of 67 male and female students who were selected purposively from the population of the study. Table 1 below presents the sample of the study following the different variables.

Table 1: Sample of the Study

Variable	Class	Number of Observations	Percentage
Gender	Male	54	80.60
	Female	13	19.40
	Total	67	100.00
Academic Level	Third year	37	55.22
	Fourth year	30	44.78
	Total	67	100.00
Place of Residence	City	22	32.84
	Village	38	56.72
	Refugee camp	7	10.45
	Total	67	100.00

3.3 Instruments of the Study

To achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers designed a tool for the purpose of data collection. The tool was designed based on empirical resources similar to the topics of a number of studies, such as Makhoulf, (2011), Al-Weisi (2009), and Omar (2009). The responses of the subjects of the study on the tool were tested following Leekirt scale. In addition, the researchers applied Triple Grade Scale for the purpose of data analysis and to determine the responses of the sample of the study. These include:

- Means of estimates between 1 and 2.23 against low grade estimate
- Means of estimates between 20.34 and 3.67 against moderate grade estimates
- Means of estimates between 3.68 and 5 against high grade estimates

3.4 Validity of Instruments

The tool validity was calculated using content validity, and it was approved by a number of referees who gave their opinions and judgments as to its domains and items and whether the items matched the domains or not. In view of the referees' judgments, some items were added and others were dropped. Finally, the questionnaire came out in its present shape with 45 items.

3.5 Consistency of Instruments

The internal consistency coefficient of the whole tool was calculated, including all its six domains, through using Cronbach Alpha. The consistency coefficients were high, and therefore were accepted by the researchers.

Table 2: Consistency of the domain of life skills according to Cronbach Alpha scale for internal consistency

#	Item/ Skill	Number of Observations	Value on Chronbach Alpha
1	Physical & Efficiency	10	0.835
2	Thinking & Discovery	10	0.830
3	Mental	9	0.759
4	Social	8	0.877
5	Communication	8	0.832
6	Total	45	0.937

The details in Table 2 show that Chronbach Alpha values for the different domains are 0.835 for physical and efficiency skills, 0.830 for thinking and discovery skills, 0.759 for mental skills, 0.877 for social skills, 0.823 for communication and correspondence skills,

and finally 0.937 for the questionnaire. All these values are high enough to meet the objectives of the present study.

3.6 Procedures

Having selected the sample from the third and fourth year students enrolled in the Physical Education Department of Al-Quds University, the researchers distributed the questionnaire to the students during classes.

3.7 Variables of the Study

This study is made up of the following variables:

- **Independent variables**, including the variables of gender (male, female), academic level (third year, fourth year), and place of residence (city, village, camp).
- **Dependent variables**, including the variables of life skills acquired by the students of physical education at Al-Quds University.

3.8 Statistical Analysis

To respond to the questions of the study, the data collected was processed via SPSS. The data statistical processing operations included the calculation of percentages, means, standard deviations, one way ANOVA, T test, and Cronbach's alpha.

4. Results and Discussion

Question one: What are the life skills acquired by the students enrolled in the Department of Physical Education at Al-Quds University?

To answer this question, the means and standard deviations were calculated.

Table 3: means and standard deviations for the life skills of the students of the Physical Department

#	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Level	Rank
4	Social	3.99	0.62	79.80	High	1
3	Mental	3.95	0.47	79.00	High	2
5	Communication	3.87	0.55	77.40	High	3
1	Physical & Kinetic	3.86	0.51	77.20	High	4
2	Thinking & Discovery	3.76	0.5	75.20	High	5
	Total	3.89	0.42	77.80	High	

The above table shows that the life skills acquired by the students of the Physical Education Department are of high values. The mean is 3.89 with a significance of 77.80. The value of the total skills is high, and it ranges between 3.99 and 3.76. The social skills come second in the hierarchy, with a mean of 3.99 and a significance of 79.80. The skills of thinking and discovery come in the last place with a mean of 3.76 and a significance of 75.20.

The findings of the study show that level of the life skills acquired by the members of the sample is higher than all other domains. The researchers maintain that the program of Physical Education is the richest in terms of the life skills necessary for building a complete and balanced character through the various educational experiences it poses. It is that the life skills acquired in physical education classes help students meet modern life demands. This result of the present study matches a group of similar studies, including Abu Tami' (2009), Al-Soteri (2007), Weis (2007), Goudas et al (2006), yet it does not match both Al-Hayek et al (2008) and Al-Hayek and Battayneh (2007).

The domains of the life skills acquired by the students of physical education at A-Quds University were analyzed as follows:

A. First, Physical and Efficiency Skills

Table 4: Means and standard deviations for the physical and efficiency skills

#	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Level	Rank
1	Fitness	3.82	0.65	76.40	High	5
2	Upright Stature	3.78	0.73	75.60	High	7
3	Sport Exercises	3.97	0.85	79.40	High	2
4	Basic Skills of Sport Games	3.75	0.91	82.00	High	1
5	Appropriate Sport Performance	4.1	0.72	75.00	High	9
6	Competing when Performing Sport Games	3.81	0.80	76.20	High	6
7	Passing Physical and Efficiency Tests	3.96	0.71	79.20	High	3
8	Easy Learning of Life Skills	3.94	0.76	78.80	High	4
9	Physical and Skill Efficiency	3.76	0.89	75.20	High	8
10	Neuromuscular Consistency	3.7	0.89	74.00	High	10
	Physical and Skill Efficiency	3.86	0.51	77.20	High	

The table shows that the level of physical and efficiency skills is considerably high, where the mean is 3.86 with a significance of 77.20. The level of skill items is high with a

mean ranging between 3.70-4.10. Item 4, which is the possessing of the basic skills of physical education, comes in the first place with a mean of 4.10 and a significance of 82.00. The skill of acquiring neuromuscular agreement, item 10, comes last with a mean of 3.70 and a significance of 74.00.

According to the table, the physical and efficiency skills are of high level. The researchers attribute this to the fact that the practical courses and the sport games of the physical education program focus on building physical and efficiency skills. These results are similar to the results of the study of Hammaoudeh (2007).

B. Second: Thinking and Discovery Skills

Table 5: Means and standard deviations for the skills of thinking and discovery

#	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Level	Rank
1	Collective Thinking	3.82	0.63	76.40	High	4
2	Reaching Various Solutions of the Same Problem	3.87	0.57	77.40	High	2
3	Interpreting Results	3.84	0.73	76.80	High	3
4	Linking Educational Experiences with Similar Life Experiences	3.75	0.82	75.00	High	7
5	Leadership Thinking	3.76	0.78	75.20	High	6
6	Organizing Ideas	3.79	0.96	75.80	High	5
7	Creative Thinking	3.91	0.77	78.20	High	1
8	Predicting	3.61	0.85	72.20	Medium	9
9	Predicting	3.66	0.84	73.20	Medium	8
10	?????	3.55	0.84	71.00	Medium	10
	Thinking and Discovery	3.76	0.50	75.20	High	

It can be noticed that the level of the skills of thinking and discovery is high. The means is 3.76 with a significance of 75.2. The level of the items of this domain ranges from moderate to high. The means are between 3.55 and 3.91. Item 7 comes in the first place; it is the ability to organize thoughts in a logical way, the mean is 3.91 with a significance of 78.20. Item, 10, the ability to predict the desired performance, comes in the last place, with a mean of 3.5 and a significance of 71.0.

The findings of the study show that the kills of thinking and discovery are of high level. The researchers think that the physical education curriculum improves all mental performances, including memorizing, thinking, recalling, analyzing, constructing, and evaluation, through the different games athletes play and through

integrating physical education and sport games with life experiences. This result of the study is consistent with Tami' (2009), Wafi (2010), and Sugiyamak et al. (2008).

C. Third, Mental Skills

Table 6: Means and standard deviations of mental skills

#	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Level	Rank
1	Respecting Others	4.27	0.77	85.40	High	1
2	Accepting Criticism & Self-Criticism	3.63	0.88	72.60	High	9
3	Bearing Responsibility	4.07	0.74	81.40	High	2
4	Expressing Thoughts Clearly	3.88	0.73	77.60	High	6
5	Clear Verbal Performance	4.04	0.77	80.80	High	4
	Listening to Others Clearly					
7	Expressing Personal Traits in The Presence of Others	4.07	0.74	81.40	High	7
8	Sharing Opinions	3.76	0.87	75.20	High	3
9	Taking Initiative	3.99	0.84	79.80	High	8
	Mental Skills	3.95	0.47	79.00	High	5

As shown in the table above, the level of mental skills is high. The means is 3.95, with a significance of 79.00. The level of skills ranges between moderate and high, where the means are between 3.03 and 4.27. The mean of the skill of respecting others is 4.27, with a significance of 85.40, whereas the item of criticism and self-criticism has a mean of 3.63 and significance of 72.60.

According to Table 6, the acquired mental skills have a high level and the researchers refer this to the fact that the curriculum enhances the students' skills of bearing responsibility, expressing personal traits, respecting others, determination, persistence, and firm willpower. This result of the study is consistence with the results of Al-Wesei (2009) and Soutari et al. (2009).

D. Forth, Social Skills

The means and standard deviations of the impact of the physical education curriculum on social skills are expressed in table 7 below.

Table 7: Means and standard deviations of the impact of the
Physical Education curriculum on social skills

#	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Level	Rank
1	Treating Other People Properly	4.25	0.75	85.00	High	1
2	Team Work	4.16	0.81	83.20	High	2
3	Respecting and Accepting Others	4.13	0.83	82.60	High	3
4	Giving Priority to Group Interests	3.88	0.88	77.60	High	6
5	Adapting to Social Situations	3.90	0.80	78.00	High	5
6	Trusting Same Group Individuals	3.63	01.01	72.60	High	5
7	Coping with Collective Work Pressure	3.84	0.73	76.80	High	87
8	Helping Others	3.13	0.94	82.60	High	3
	Social Skills	3.99	0.62	79.80	high	

Table 7 above shows that the level of social skills is high. The mean is 3.99 with a significance of 79.80. The level of items ranges between moderate and high, where the means are between 3.63 and 4.25. The item of treating others improperly comes in the first position, with a mean of 4.25 and a significance of 85.00. The item of trusting same group members comes last, with a mean of 3.63 and significance of 72.60.

The level of social skills is high, which entails that the physical education curriculum of Al-Quds University has a significant role in the social bringing up of the subjects, including reinforcing team work, helping others, watching group interests, ...etc. These are similar to the results arrived at by Soutari et al (2009), Abu Tami' (2009), and Goudas (2006), yet are different from Al-Hayek and Batayneh (2007), Al-Hayek et al (2007, and Al-Hayek (2007).

E. Fifth, Communication Skills

Table 8 below shows the means and standard deviations of communication skills examined by the study:

Table 8: Means and standard deviations of communication skills

#	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Level	Rank
1	Expressing Opinion	3.97	0.80	79.40	High High	3
2	Employing Different Communication Means	3.73	0.81	74.60	High	7
3	Ability to Convince	3.85	0.84	77.00	High	5
4	Moving From One Topic to Another Smoothly	3.85	0.82	77.00	High	5
5	Expressing Personal Views in Public	4.09	0.79	81.80	High	1
6	Proper Communication	4.01	0.75	80.20	High	2
7	Talking for Long Time	3.57	1.02	71.40	Moderate	8
8	Initiating Conversation	3.87	0.74	77.40	High	4
	Communication Skills	3.87	0.55	77.40	High	

The level of the skill of communication is high, with a mean of 3.87 and significance of 77.40. The level of this skill on this scale is between moderate and high, where the means are between 3.57 and 4.09. Item 5, comes in the first place with a mean of 4.09 and a relative significance of 81.80. In the final place comes item 7 with a mean of 3.57 and a significance of 71.40.

The researchers maintain that the efficiency of an individual should be measured in light of what he/she contributes to his society rather than just what they know. Therefore, life skills have a major role in qualifying and training youth, as a human source, to bring about development and interact positively with other people.

Question two: Are there any statistically significant differences at the level of $0.05 \geq \alpha$ in view of the students' opinions in the life skills acquired by the enrolling student which can be attributed to sex, academic level and place of residence.

Table 9: Calculated means and standard deviations as for the variable of sex

Skill	Sex	Number of Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	T value	Percentage
Physical and total efficiency	Male	54	3.86	0.54	0.21	0.829
	Female	13	3.83	0.37		
Thinking and discovery	Male	54	3.72	0.51	1.30	0.197
	Female	13	3.92	0.42		
Mental	Male	54	3.92	0.47	1.27	0.206
	Female	13	4.10	0.48		

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Social	Male	54	4.01	0.67	0.43	0.666
	Female	13	3.92	0.39		
Communication	Male	54	3.85	0.58	0.40	0.689
	Female	13	3.92	0.43		
Overall skills	Male	54	3.3.87	0.44	0.50	0.613
	Female	13	3.94	0.37		

The data in table 9 show that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of $0.05 \geq \alpha$ between the means calculated that can be attributed to sex based on T value of 0.50. The value is 0.613 for the total grade, which is not statistically significant. The calculated T values are 0.21 with a significance of 0.613 for physical and efficiency skills, 1.30 with a significance of 0.197 for thinking and discovery skill, 1.27 with a significance of 0.206 for mental skill, 0.43 with a significance of 0.666 for social skill, and finally 0.40 with a significance 0.689 for communication skill. All these values are not statistically significance since the value of significance level is over 0.05.

The study shows that there are no statistically significant differences attributed to sex. The researchers assume that both male and female students have the same skills because the educational experiences and the curricula are shared by both genders. These results comply with Wafi (2010), Abu Tami' (2009), and Al-Hayek and Battayneh (2007) in terms of the absence of differences in integrating life skills with the physical education curricula of the University of Jordan. Yet, the results in this domain are similar to Al-Yahkek et al. (2007).

Table 10: Results of T test for the differences between the means of life skills acquired by the subjects of the study attributed to academic level

Skill	Academic level	Number of Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	T value	Percentage
Physical and efficiency	3 rd year	37	3.89	0.49	0.55	0.581
	4 th year	30	3.82	0.53		
Thinking and discovery	3 rd year	37	3.79	0.45	0.66	0.506
	4 th year	30	3.71	0.55		
mental	3 rd year	37	4.06	0.45	2.04	0.045
	4 th year	30	3.83	0.47		
Social	3 rd year	37	4.10	0.50	1.69	0.096
	4 th year	30	3.85	0.73		
Communication	3 rd year	37	3.96	0.47	1.47	0.146
	4 th year	30	3.76	0.63		
Overall skills	3 rd year	37	3.96	0.40	1.62	0.109
	4 th year	30	3.79	0.45		

The results presented in table 10 show that there are no statistically significance differences at $0.05 \geq \alpha$ between the means calculated on life skills acquired by the subjects of the study attributed to the academic level based on T value of 1.62 for or the total grade. The calculated T value for the physical and efficiency skills is 0.55 with a significance level of 0.581, 0.66 for thinking and discovery skill with a significance level of 0.506, 1.69 for social skills with a significance of 0.096, and 1.47 for communication skills with a significance level of 0.146. These values are not statistically significant since the levels are over 0.05, except for the T value calculated for mental skill which is 2.04 with a significance level of 0.045. This value is not statistically significant because the significance value is below 0.05.

The results are not statistically significant with regard to the variable of academic level. The researchers see that third and fourth year students almost take similar courses in physical education. This result is similar to Al-Hayek (2009) and Al-Hayek et al (2008).

Third: The results calculated for the variable of place of residence

Table 11: Means and standard deviations for the life skills acquired by the subjects of the study attributed to the place of residence

Skill	Residence	Number of observations	Mean	Standard Deviation
Physical and efficiency	City	22	3.80	0.55
	Village	38	3.97	0.44
	Refugee camp	7	3.41	0.47
Thinking & discovery	City	22	3.78	0.58
	Village	38	3.78	0.47
	Refugee camp	7	3.56	0.39
Mental	City	22	4.02	0.50
	Village	38	3.95	0.45
	Refugee camp	7	3.75	0.47
Social	City	22	3.86	0.84
	Village	38	4.09	0.46
	Refugee camp	7	3.88	0.61
Communication	City	22	3.74	0.70
	Village	38	3.97	0.44
	Refugee camp	7	3.68	0.53
All skills	City	22	3.84	0.53
	Village	38	3.95	0.33
	Refugee camp	7	3.65	0.44

The results show that there are no statistically significant differences attributed to place of residence between the means calculated for the life skills acquired by the subjects of the study. To determine whether these differences are statistically significant or not at $0.05 \geq \alpha$, the researchers applied one way ANOVA as presented in table 12 below.

Table 12: Results of applied one way ANOVA

Skill	Source of difference	Total squared values	Degrees	Means of squared values	F Value	Significance
Physical and efficiency	Between Groups	1.93	2	0.96	4.13	0.021
	Within Same Group	14.94	64	0.23		
	Total	16.86	66			
Thinking and discovery	Between Groups	0.31	2	0.15	0.62	0.543
	Within Same Group	15.92	64	0.25		
	Total	116.23	66			
Mental	Between Group	0.40	2	0.20	0.90	0.413
	Within Same Group	14.25	64	0.22		
	Total	14.65	66			
Social	Between Group	0.79	2	0.40	1.02	0.365
	Within Same Group	24.72	64	0.39		
	Total	25.51	66			
Communication	Between Groups	1.01	2	0.51	1.70	0191
	Within Same Group	19.05	64	0.30		
	Total	20.06	66			
All skills	Between Groups	0.59	2	0.29	1.67	0.197
	Within Same Group	11.26	64	0.18		
	Total	11.85	66			

The results in table 12 show that there are no statistically significant differences at $0.05 \geq \alpha$ level between the means calculated on the life skills acquired by the subjects of

the study that are attributed to place of residence based on T value of 1.67 and significance level of 0.197 for the total grade. The study shows that F values are as follows: 0.62 for thinking and discovery skill with a significance level of 0.543; 0.90 for mental skills with a significance level of 0.413; 1.02 for social skills with a significance level of 0.365; and 1.07 for communication skills with a significance level of 0.191. These values are not statistically significant since their level is over 0.05, except for the physical and efficiency skills, where the calculated F value is 4.13 with a significance level of 0.021, which means that this value is not statistically significant, for the value is below 0.05.

To determine the sources of these differences, the researchers applied Shefeih scale as shown in table 13 below:

Table 13: Results of applied Shefeih scale

Skill	Mean	Residence	Village	Refugee Camp
Physical and Efficiency	3.80	City		
	3.97	Village		
	3.41	Refugee Camp		

Table 13 above presents the results of Shefieh's test for post comparisons to determine the sources of differences in physical and efficiency skills attributed to place of residence.

The results indicate that there are statistically significant differences between village residents and refugee camp residents for the benefit of village residents. The only statistical significant difference calculated is in the physical skills. The researchers attributed this to the similar living conditions of both groups, such as life pressures and challenges.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

1. Students enrolled in the physical education program of Al-Quds University highly obtain life skills;
2. Social skills are obtained more than any other skills by the students in the physical education program;
3. There are no statistically significant differences in the level of life skills obtained by the students of the physical education program which can be attributed to the variables of sex, academic level or place of residence.

At the end of the study, the researchers recommended the following:

1. The necessity for integrating life skills in the educational process;
2. Linking educational skills with life skills;

3. Designing and holding courses and workshops for academics and students to explain the concept of life skills and how they can be integrated in the curriculum.

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